

Local Government in Italy

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Italy	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Italy: An Introduction	5
2.2. <i>Public-Private Partnerships and Social Housing</i>	7
2.3. <i>Bridging the Urban-Rural Digital Divide</i>	11
2.4. <i>Strategic Planning in Geographically Heterogeneous Metropolises</i>	18
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Italy: An Introduction.....	24
3.2. <i>Investment Spending of Local Entities</i>	28
3.3. <i>The Revision of the Inter-Municipal Equalization Mechanism in Trentino</i>	31
3.4. <i>Financial Assistance to Municipalities with Structural Deficits</i>	36
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Italy: An Introduction	42
4.2. <i>Unions of Municipalities in Emilia-Romagna</i>	50
4.3. <i>Mergers of Municipalities – A Comparison of Procedures and Their Implications</i>	54
4.4. <i>The Valley Communities (comunità di valle) in the Province of Trento</i>	59
4.5. <i>Inter-municipal Cooperation Based on a Model Agreement: A Top-Down Approach in South Tyrol</i>	63
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Italy: An Introduction.....	71
5.2. <i>The Inclusion of Local Governments in Italy’s Multilevel Conference System of Intergovernmental Relations</i>	74
5.3. <i>The Council of Municipalities of South Tyrol as Facilitator of Local-Subnational Relations</i>	79
5.4. <i>Migration Management as an Intergovernmental Cooperation Instrument in Rural Areas</i>	83
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Italy: An Introduction	91
6.2. <i>Participatory Budgeting in Italy: The Case of the Municipality of Mals</i>	94
6.3. <i>District Laboratories (‘laboratori di quartiere’) in the City of Bologna</i>	99
6.4. <i>Regulations on Common Goods</i>	103

People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Italy: An Introduction

Martina Trettel, *Eurac Research*

In recent years, representative democracy has been experiencing a crisis in relation to all levels of government: local, provincial, regional, national and supranational. The most striking evidence of this crisis are the low turnout at the polls and the widespread disinterest in issues linked to society and citizenship. Although it is recognized that the instruments of representative democracy, elections in particular, are still the method that allows modern systems to be governed democratically, a new phenomenon is slowly taking hold: that of 'participatory democracy'.

'Participatory democracy' can be intended as the synthesis of practices, devices and procedures that create ways for citizens to be actively and effectively involved in decision-making processes of public administrations. In other words, these are 'processes or institutions, that are new to a policy issue, policy role, or level of governance, and developed to reimagine and deepen the role of citizens in governance processes by increasing opportunities for participation, deliberation and influence'.¹⁷⁴ The purpose of this innovative policy-making tools is to enhance the legitimacy of political decisions, to improve the quality of democratic policymaking, and, finally, to increase their level of effectiveness.

In recent years, in particular at local level, a growing interest in the instruments of participatory democracy can be witnessed.¹⁷⁵ In line with this tendency, also many Italian municipalities are employing more and more frequently decision-making tools that are intended to involve common citizens in the traditional (representative) decision-making structures. The Italian constitutional structure allows municipalities, even if not explicitly, to adopt regulations that introduce consultative participatory procedures. This has been also confirmed by the Italian Constitutional Court.¹⁷⁶

The Italian Constitution does not contain any explicit reference to participatory democracy and its democratic nature is based on Article 1 (particularly paragraph 2) which regulates the principle of popular sovereignty. The democratic principle is concretely implemented through instruments of representative and direct democracy, explicitly provided for by the constitutional text. Nonetheless, a constitutional connection to participatory democracy can be identified in Article 3 paragraph 2 of the Constitution, which provides for '...(the) effective

¹⁷⁴ Stephen Elstub and Oliver Escobar 'Defining and Typologising Democratic Innovations' in Stephen Elstub and Oliver Escobar (eds), *Handbook of Democratic Innovation and Governance* (Edward Elgar 2019).

¹⁷⁵ Birte Gundelach, Patricia Buser and Daniel Kübler, 'Deliberative Democracy in Local Governance. The Impact of Institutional Design on Legitimacy' (2017) 43 *Local Government Studies* 218.

¹⁷⁶ Constitutional Court, Judgement no 379/2004; Constitutional Court, Judgement no 235/2018.

participation of all workers in the political, economic and social organization of the Country'.¹⁷⁷ In addition, Article 118 paragraph 4 of the Constitution stipulates that 'State, Regions, metropolitan Cities, Provinces and Municipalities encourage the autonomous initiative of citizens, individuals and associates, for the conduct of general interest activities, based upon the principle of subsidiarity'. This is the principle of horizontal subsidiarity that paves the way for forms of collaboration between citizens and administrations as part of the management of material and concrete activities, rather than the development of general legislative acts.¹⁷⁸

With particular regard to the local system, the ways in which citizens can participate in decision-making processes are, to one extent, traditional instruments of representative democracy, in particular elections of the local council, and that of direct democracy, like consultative referenda; on the other hand, municipalities can adopt regulations for promoting the participation of citizens in local decision-making, as stated by Article 8 of the Consolidated Law on Local Authorities.¹⁷⁹ This norm represents the legislative translation of Article 3(2) of the Constitution. The provision stipulates that the municipalities must promote organizations of participation in the local administration, by way of the introduction in their statutes of 'forms of consultation of the population as well as procedures for the admission of requests, petitions and proposals of individual or associated citizens aimed at promoting interventions for the best protection of collective interests'. The Consolidated Law on Local Authorities is the source that underpins formal legitimacy and the extent of the municipal regulatory competence in terms of adoption of institutes of participatory democracy.

According to Valastro,¹⁸⁰ about a third of the Italian municipalities have equipped themselves, over time, with one or more regulations that in various ways regulate participatory democracy procedures. Looking at the ca. 8,000 Italian municipalities almost 3,000 regulations can be identified: a rather high number if we consider that the first ones have begun to be approved at the beginning of the 1980s. With regard to the geographical distribution, the regulations are spread all over the country with a prevalence to be identified in the northeastern regions that are characterized by a high density of municipalities.

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¹⁷⁷ Pier Luigi Zampetti, 'L'art. 3 della Costituzione e il nuovo concetto di democrazia partecipativa' in *Studi per il ventesimo anniversario dell'assemblea costituente* (vol 2, Vallecchi 1969).

¹⁷⁸ Francesco ME Emmanuele, 'La sfida della sussidiarietà ed il nuovo assetto istituzionale' (2006) 4 *Federalismi.it*.

¹⁷⁹ Italian Legislative Decree no 276/2000.

¹⁸⁰ Alessandra Valastro, 'La democrazia partecipativa alla prova dei territori: tendenze e prospettive dei regolamenti comunali' (2016) 3 *Osservatorio sulle fonti* 1.

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